

Research Internship

Novel Optimization Model Applied for Decarbonization Scenarios of Non-Interconnected Mediterranean Islands – A Kastellorizo Case Study

Advisor	Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Hamacher Chair of Renewable and Sustainable Energy Systems
Submitted by	Lampros Konstantellos Lichtenbergstraße 4a 85748 Garching +49 89 289 52741
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Abstract

This research internship focuses on transforming the electrical power system of Kastellorizo, a Greek non-interconnected island heavily reliant on polluting diesel generation, into a decarbonized system. This transition is motivated by the imperative to reduce carbon dioxide emissions and the high cost associated with diesel-based electricity production. The study assesses various aspects, including energy demand, solar and wind potential, and the integration of electric vehicles to achieve a fully decarbonized system. Two scenarios are presented: scenario 1 incorporates open field and rooftop photovoltaics, along with an onshore wind farm, while scenario 2 relies solely on solar energy. Both scenarios aim to phase out the diesel power plant by 2052. Detailed analyses of installed capacities for the diesel power plant, renewable energy sources, and the required battery energy storage system for meeting the demand are provided for each scenario. This research internship identifies potential locations for renewable infrastructure, highlighting the wind and solar energy potential on Kastellorizo and the nearby Stroggili islet. Additionally, it proposes the transformation of diesel power plants into biofuel-based facilities to enhance the reduction of carbon dioxide emissions. Overall, this research internship offers a comprehensive strategy for Kastellorizo's energy transition, aligning with local and national targets.

keywords - **decarbonization, non-interconnected islands, renewable energy sources, energy transition, climate change, biofuels, Kastellorizo**

Acronyms

ATC Average Total Cost

AVC Average Variable Cost

BESS Battery Energy Storage System

CO2 Carbon Dioxide

EV Electric Vehicle

FLH Full Load Hours

HEDNO Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator

NIDP Non-Interconnected Islands Development Program

PPC Hellenic Public Power Corporation

PV Photovoltaic

pyGRETA python Generator of REnewable Time series and mAps

RAE Hellenic Regulatory Authority for Energy

RES Renewable Energy Sources

TS Time Series

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivation

By the end of 2021, Greece had a total of 29 non-interconnected islands to the mainland[1]. The reliance of these islands on polluting sources, such as diesel and heavy oil, for electricity generation underscores the urgent need for a transformation in their electrical power systems[2]. This reliance results in high CO₂ emissions and is also associated with increased electricity production cost. Notably, 10 out of 29 non-interconnected islands, including Kastellorizo, rely entirely on diesel for electricity generation, lacking renewable energy sources (RES) integration[3][4]. This exclusive dependence on diesel aggravates environmental concerns and requires a substantial overhaul of the energy infrastructure on these islands, towards a decarbonized future. Greece's 2021-2030 Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan targets a 35% share of RES in overall gross energy consumption, with a focus on increasing their share in the electricity sector to at least 60% and in the heating and cooling sector to 42.5% by 2030, while also aiming to raise their share in transport to 19% from 6.6% in 2020[1].

1.2 Objective of the Research Internship

The main objective of this research internship is to thoroughly analyze and examine the transition potential of Kastellorizo from a conventional energy supply to a fully renewable-based system. Additionally, the feasibility of transitioning the transportation sector of Kastellorizo to rely on electric vehicles (EVs), contributing to the decarbonization of the island will be explored.

1.3 Scope of the Report

This report documents the technical, economic, and model analysis of transitioning Kastellorizo from a conventional energy supply to a renewable-based system while minimizing the environmental impact of developing renewable energy infrastructure. It examines the existing diesel-based electrical power system, projects energy demand, evaluates solar and wind energy potential and proposes decarbonization strategies for the island in alignment with local and national targets and utilize renewable energy potential[5][6]. Two scenarios are presented based on a

linear programming optimization model to determine the most cost-effective energy system configuration to meet predefined demand time series (TS). These scenarios offer diverse pathways for the island's decarbonized electricity generation, addressing financial feasibility with a focus on long-term climate benefits and economic sustainability. The option of connecting Kastellorizo to other locations within Greece, such as Rhodes, as well as international connections to Cyprus or Turkey, falls outside the scope of this study.

1.4 The Island of Kastellorizo

Kastellorizo[7], officially known as Megisti, is a Greek island and municipality located within the Dodecanese archipelago in the Mediterranean Sea[8]. It covers an area of 9.113 km² and has a population of 584 permanent residents according to the 2021 census[9]. Kastellorizo is renowned for its serene beauty and rich cultural heritage. Located approximately 570 km southeast of Athens and 125 km east of Rhodes, Kastellorizo is an integral part of the Rhodes regional unit.

Figure 1.1 Satellite image of Kastellorizo[10]

1.5 Energy Challenges and Solutions on Kastellorizo

Kastellorizo, marked by significant summer tourist activity, stands out as one of the most energy-intensive non-interconnected island electrical power systems, not connected to the mainland grid[3][11]. The reliance on diesel-based electricity genera-

tion not only leads to environmental consequences but also results in high electricity production cost, with the average annual total cost of the last 5 years exceeding 500€/MWh[11]. These costs indirectly burden consumers through public service obligations. Additionally, its geographical location and the economic activities of its residents directly influence the delineation of the Greek Exclusive Economic Zone, emphasizing the strategic importance of the island. Given these challenges, it is imperative to explore the potential of RES, such as rooftop and open-field photovoltaics and wind turbines. Furthermore, by incorporating energy storage systems, the island can completely eliminate its reliance on diesel for electricity production. This transition will have several positive outcomes, including lower electricity expenses and a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

Figure 1.2 Map of the Hellenic Electricity Transmission System[12].

Chapter 2

Tools Used

2.1 urbs

An open-source linear programming optimization model that addresses capacity expansion planning and unit commitment in distributed energy systems. With a focus on optimal storage sizing and utilization, urbs is designed for multi-commodity energy systems. Its primary function is to determine the most cost-effective energy system configuration to meet predefined demand TS, including multiple commodities such as electricity. By default, urbs operates on hourly time steps, offering a flexible and detailed approach to energy system optimization[13].

2.2 pyGRETA

An open-source software tool that assesses renewable energy potential and generates high-resolution maps and TS for user-defined regions globally. It models various renewable technologies, utilizes advanced data sources, and offers versatile applications, making it a valuable resource for precise renewable energy assessments[14].

Chapter 3

Electrical Power System Overview

3.1 Current State of the Electrical Power System

The autonomous electrical power system on Kastellorizo stands as one of the 10 out of the 29 non-interconnected island electrical power systems in Greece that lack integration of RES[4].

According to the data provided by the General Directorate of Thermal and Hydro-electric Production of the Hellenic Public Power Corporation (PPC) to the Hellenic Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE), as of February 2023, the electrical power system on Kastellorizo is currently supplied by a 2.22 MW diesel power plant consisting of seven diesel generator units, as detailed in Table 3.1. These units operate as base or peak load units, depending on their availability and the variation in the electrical power system load.

During summer the diesel power plant has a maximum gross rated power of 1.91 MW, but in heatwave conditions, the maximum gross rated power decreases to 1.64 MW, and during winter, it increases to 2.09 MW, as illustrated in the Table 3.2.

Unit Number	Model	Nominal Power (MW)	License Expiration Year
G1	VOLVO PENTA TAD 1645GE	0.40	2052
G2	VOLVO PENTA TAD 1645GE	0.40	2052
G3	CUMMINS VT 1710G	0.45	2038
G4	VOLVO PENTA TAD 1345GE	0.25	2030
G5	HYUNDAI KD8AX	0.22	2038
G6	DOOSAN P158LE-2	0.25	2038
G7	DOOSAN P158LE-2	0.25	2038
Total		2.22	

Table 3.1 Details of Kastellorizo Diesel Power Plant Generator Units[2]

Unit Number	Maximum Gross Rated Power in Winter (MW)	Maximum Gross Rated Power in Summer (MW)	Maximum Gross Rated Power in Heatwave (MW)
G1	0.40	0.32	0.32
G2	0.40	0.32	0.32
G3	0.40	0.40	0.31
G4	0.25	0.25	0.18
G5	0.20	0.18	0.15
G6	0.22	0.22	0.18
G7	0.22	0.22	0.18
Total	2.09	1.91	1.64

Table 3.2 Maximum Gross Rated Power of Kastellorizo Diesel Power Plant Units in Different Seasons[2]

(a) External View

(b) Control Panel

Figure 3.1 VOLVO Unit at Kastellorizo Diesel Power Plant[15]

3.2 Electricity Production Cost

Electricity production on Kastellorizo is associated with a substantial annual average variable cost (AVC) of 339.58€/MWh in 2022, primarily driven by the high expenses of diesel. In 2022, the total annual electricity production cost for Kastellorizo amounted to 2,152,569€, equivalent to an annual average total cost (ATC) of 489.78€/MWh, considering the island’s total demand of 4,395 MWh[11][16].

These statistics underscore the pressing necessity of incorporating RES into the island’s electricity production framework. The Table 3.3 provides the annual AVC and ATC of Kastellorizo for the years 2018-2022, and the Figure 3.2 illustrates the annual total cost of Kastellorizo’s energy production for the same period, based on the demand Table 4.1 indicates.

Year	Annual AVC (€/MWh)	Annual ATC (€/MWh)
2018	273.77	507.28
2019	284.97	555.90
2020	239.50	501.04
2021	260.88	460.64
2022	339.58	489.78

Table 3.3 Annual AVC & ATC for Kastellorizo (2018-2022)[11]

Figure 3.2 Annual Total Electricity Production Cost for Kastellorizo (2018-2022)[11][3]

Chapter 4

Demand Data

4.1 Annual Electricity Demand

The annual demand data for Kastellorizo for the years 2018-2022 were obtained from the Public Consultation conducted by the RAE as part of the Non-Interconnected Islands Development Program (NIDP) for the 2023-2029 period[17].

The detailed hourly demand TS for the year 2022, totalling 8,760 hours, were provided by the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO) and were utilized as input for the optimization model in the aforementioned year [16].

Year	Demand (MWh)	Variation
2018	3,762	-
2019	3,866	2.76%
2020	3,585	-7.27%
2021	3,825	6.69%
2022	4,395	14.90%

Table 4.1 Annual Electricity Demand Data for Kastellorizo (2018-2022)[17][16]

4.1.1 Tourism Activity for the Years 2018-2022

The Table 4.1 illustrates a consistent upward trend in the island's electricity demand, with increases observed in nearly every year. The decrease in demand in the year 2020 was primarily a result of the COVID-19 outbreak, which led to a limitation in tourist activity on the island according to the Figure 4.1, depicting port and air arrivals in Kastellorizo for the same period. This decrease indicates the significant impact tourism can have on the island's overall demand. In 2022, the recovery of tourist activity led to a remarkable 14.90% increase in electricity demand.

Figure 4.1 Arrivals in Kastellorizo (2018-2022)[18]

From 2018 to 2022, Kastellorizo experienced an average annual passenger arrival of 12,974, with a peak of 18,164 arrivals in 2022 and a low of 9,656 in 2020[18]. Considering that the island has 584 permanent residents according to the 2021 census[9], this signifies that in a span of 5 years, the average arrivals in Kastellorizo exceeded its permanent residents by more than 22 times.

In more detail, for the same period, the average annual port arrivals amounted to 10,525, accounting for 81.13% of the total average arrivals per year. Additionally, the average annual air arrivals totaled at 2,448, making up the remaining 18.87% of the total average arrivals per year.

4.1.2 Seasonal Tourism Influence on 2022 Electricity Demand

The Table 4.2 provides a visual representation of the variations of electricity demand on Kastellorizo throughout the year. August stands out as the month with the highest demand, reaching a peak of 1.2162 MW at the 5,563rd hour of the year, specifically on August 20, 2022, at 19:00. When the summer period is excluded, the average monthly demand is 314 MWh. However, during the summer months, the average monthly demand surges to 522 MWh. This indicates that during the summer season, the demand increases by a substantial 66.32%.

Month	Demand (MWh)	Variation
January	328	-
February	270	-17.47%
March	309	14.35%
April	237	-23.30%
May	274	15.74%
June	351	27.98%
July	533	51.78%
August	683	28.15%
September	481	-29.63%
October	358	-25.62%
November	281	-21.54%
December	290	3.26%
Total	4,395	

Table 4.2 Monthly Electricity Demand for Kastellorizo in 2022[16]

When the variations in demand and air arrivals throughout the year are visualized on a single chart, as depicted in the Figure 4.2, it becomes clear that they both follow a parallel trend. This chart effectively underscores the direct correlation between the two, reaffirming the substantial impact of tourism on the increase in electricity demand on the island.

Figure 4.2 Monthly Air Arrivals & Electricity Demand for 2022 in Kastellorizo[16][18]

4.2 Annual Electricity Demand Projections

The annual demand projections for Kastellorizo for the years 2023-2029 in the Table 4.3 were obtained from the Public Consultation conducted by the RAE as part of the NIDP for the 2023-2029 period.

Year	Demand (MWh)	Variation
2023	5,258	19.64%
2024	5,363	2%
2025	5,470	2%
2026	5,580	2%
2027	5,691	2%
2028	5,805	2%
2029	5,921	2%
2030	6,039	2%
2038	7,076	2%
2052	9,337	2%

Table 4.3 Annual Electricity Demand Projections for Kastellorizo[17]

The projections for the years 2030, 2038, and 2052 have been used as demand input for the optimization model. The consistent 2% annual increase in demand considered for these projections is based on key factors that drive consistent demand on the island, and these are mentioned below.

Tourism: The increasing popularity of Kastellorizo, as a tourist destination, drives higher demand for accommodations, entertainment, and services, all reliant on electricity[18].

Electric Transportation: The transition of the transportation sector to EVs, encompassing electric cars, taxis, and buses for public transportation, as well as boats, requires charging infrastructure and increases the demand for electricity to meet transportation needs.

Population Growth: The expanding population of Kastellorizo leads to more households and businesses, all requiring electricity. According to the 2021 census, the permanent residents of the island have increased by 18.70% over the past decade[9].

Construction Projects and Energy-Intensive Activities: Construction projects, both residential and commercial, such as hotels, require temporary power and contribute to permanent demand once completed. Simultaneously, the expanding population leads to an increased need for energy-intensive processes like water desalination, and the energy demands of the airport rise with the growing number of tourists visiting the island each year.

4.3 Electrical Power System Parameters Projections

The Table 4.4 illustrates an upward trend, indicating a progressive increase in peak demand and load factor projections in the coming years. Of particular importance is the power deficit, a critical metric used to assess the stability and reliability of an electrical grid. The projected power deficit indicates a situation where the demand for electrical power surpasses the available supply. In simpler terms, the grid is not generating enough electricity to meet the needs of its consumers. This situation can lead to brownouts or blackouts, characterized by either a reduction in voltage or a complete loss of power in certain areas or across the grid.

Year	Peak Demand (MW)	Load Factor	Power Deficit/Surplus (MW)
2023	1.45	41.4%	-0.13
2024	1.49	41.1%	-0.17
2025	1.52	41.0%	-0.20
2026	1.56	40.8%	-0.24
2027	1.60	40.6%	-0.28
2028	1.64	40.4%	-0.32
2029	1.68	40.2%	-0.36

Table 4.4 Electrical Power System Parameters Projections for Kastellorizo (Years 2023-2029)[3]

Chapter 5

Scenarios

5.1 About the Scenarios

The scenario development process, while adaptable to all non-interconnected islands, has been specifically tailored to focus on Kastellorizo. This in-depth study has evaluated Kastellorizo’s solar potential, both open field and rooftop, wind potential, and the expiration years of licenses for the seven diesel generator units at Kastellorizo diesel power plant. These licenses are set to expire in the years 2030, 2038, and 2052[2]. Consequently, the input data for the optimization model will be aligned with these key years, including 2022 as the initial year of the simulation.

To enable a gradual reduction in diesel-based electricity generation, the diesel power plant will be divided into three sections, grouping the diesel generator units with the same license expiration year. Each section will remain operational until the expiration of its license. The first section will remain operational until 2030, the second section until 2038, and the third section until 2052, as specified in the Table 5.1. In 2052, Kastellorizo’s electricity production will have achieved complete decarbonization, relying exclusively on RES.

Section Number	Unit Number	Nominal Power (MW)	License Expiration Year
Section 1	G4	0.25	2030
	G3	0.45	2038
Section 2	G5	0.22	2038
	G6	0.25	2038
	G7	0.25	2038
Section 3	G1	0.40	2052
	G2	0.40	2052

Table 5.1 Diesel Power Plant Sections Operational Periods

The data for maximum power potential and percentage of available land for open field and rooftop photovoltaics, and the onshore wind farm, along with detailed TS data for the entire year, were provided by pyGRETA[14] and utilized as input

data for the optimization model. Additionally, located 4 km southeast of Kastellorizo, Stroggili[19] is an uninhabited islet with significant wind and solar potential. Notably, previous projects in Greece[20] have successfully installed onshore wind farms on similar uninhabited islets, demonstrating that such installations do not result in visual disturbances to the surrounding areas of Kastellorizo. This makes Stroggili an ideal location for the installation of onshore wind turbines and open field photovoltaics. Therefore, the data below include this islet in the calculation of the maximum power potential and the percentage of available land for open field photovoltaics and the onshore wind farm.

Renewable Energy Source	Maximum Power Potential (MW)	Percentage of Land Available
Open Field PVs	491	44.07%
Rooftop PVs	2.41	0.56%
Onshore Wind Farm	79	51.41%

Table 5.2 Maximum Power Potential & Percentage of Land Available for RES

Figure 5.1 Satellite image of Kastellorizo & Stroggili[10]

In alignment with the goal of achieving complete decarbonization of Kastellorizo in the year 2052, two scenarios have been formulated.

5.2 Scenario 1

In this scenario, considered and analyzed in this study, electricity will be generated from the diesel power plant, open field and rooftop photovoltaics, and a small onshore wind farm. The diesel power plant will be fully decommissioned in 2052.

5.2.1 Installed Capacities

The Table 5.3 and Figure 5.2 illustrate the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES in the key years 2022, 2030, 2038, and 2052, with the goal of achieving total decarbonization of Kastellorizo. To facilitate the gradual reduction of the diesel power plant's installed capacity, the first section of the diesel power plant will be decommissioned in 2030, the second in 2038, and the third in 2052, as outlined in section 5.1. Open field photovoltaics will be initially installed in 2038, and by 2052, their installed capacity will nearly double. The installed capacity of rooftop photovoltaics will gradually increase over these key years, initiating in 2030 and reaching the maximum power potential of 2.41 MW in 2052. The onshore wind farm will be implemented by the installation of one wind turbine in 2030, and in 2052, one more turbine will be installed to reach the proposed installed capacity of 1.12 MW.

Year	Process	Installed Capacity (MW)
2022	Diesel Power Plant	2.22
	Open Field PVs	0.00
	Rooftop PVs	0.00
	Onshore Wind Farm	0.00
2030	Diesel Power Farm	1.97
	Open Field PVs	0.00
	Rooftop PVs	0.60
	Onshore Wind Farm	0.50
2038	Diesel Power Plant	0.80
	Open Field PVs	3.58
	Rooftop PVs	1.20
	Onshore Wind Farm	0.50
2052	Diesel Power Plant	0.00
	Open Field PVs	6.72
	Rooftop PVs	2.41
	Onshore Wind Farm	1.12

Table 5.3 Scenario 1: Diesel Power Plant & RES Proposed Installed Capacities

Figure 5.2 Scenario 1: Diesel Power Plant & RES Proposed Installed Capacities

5.2.2 Battery Energy Storage System

Based on the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES for the years 2022, 2030, 2038 and 2052, as outlined in subsection 5.2.1, the capacity and power for the required battery energy storage system (BESS) for the same years, taking into account that will have a maximum storage duration of 4 hours[21], are illustrated in the Table 5.4.

Year	Capacity (MWh)	Power (MW)
2022	-	-
2030	4	1
2038	24	6
2052	51.46	13

Table 5.4 Scenario 1: BESS Capacity & Power

5.2.3 Demand Coverage

The Figure 5.3 illustrates the percentage of electricity production from the diesel power plant, open field and rooftop photovoltaics, and the onshore wind farm for the years 2022, 2030, 2038, and 2052, based on the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES and BESS capacity and power, as outlined in subsection 5.2.1 and subsection 5.2.2. In 2022, the demand is entirely supplied by the diesel power plant. In 2030, RES comprise 30% of the electricity production, increasing to 92% in 2038, and achieving complete coverage of demand in 2052.

Figure 5.3 Scenario 1: Demand Coverage Percentage

The Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5, Figure 5.6, and Figure 5.7 illustrate the TS of electricity production from the diesel power plant, open field and rooftop photovoltaics, and the onshore wind farm for the years 2022, 2030, 2038, and 2052, as well as the stored electrical energy in the BESS, based on the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES and BESS capacity and power, as outlined in subsection 5.2.1 and subsection 5.2.2.

Figure 5.4 Scenario 1: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2022

Figure 5.5 Scenario 1: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2030

Figure 5.6 Scenario 1: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2038

Figure 5.7 Scenario 1: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2052

5.2.4 Electricity Production & Distribution Schema

The Figure 5.8 illustrates the electricity production and distribution in Kastellorizo for scenario 1. Light green shading represents infrastructure initiate installation in 2030, and darker green in 2038. Light pink shading represents the diesel section decommissioned in 2030, red in 2038, and darker red in 2052.

Figure 5.8 Scenario 1: Electricity Production & Distribution Schema

5.3 Scenario 2

In this scenario, considered and analyzed in this study, electricity will be generated from the diesel power plant, and open field and rooftop photovoltaics. The diesel power plant will be fully decommissioned in 2052.

5.3.1 Installed Capacities

The Table 5.5 and Figure 5.9 illustrate the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES in the key years 2022, 2030, 2038, and 2052, with the goal of achieving total decarbonization of Kastellorizo. To facilitate the gradual reduction of the diesel power plant's installed capacity, the first section of the diesel power plant will be decommissioned in 2030, the second in 2038, and the third in 2052, as outlined in section 5.1. Open field photovoltaics will be initially installed in 2030, with their installed capacity expected to reach 3.53 MW by 2038, and more than triple by 2052. The installed capacity of rooftop photovoltaics will gradually increase over these key years, initiating in 2030 and reaching the maximum power potential of 2.41 MW in 2052.

Year	Process	Installed Capacity (MW)
2022	Diesel Power Plant	2.22
	Open Field PVs	0.00
	Rooftop PVs	0.00
2030	Diesel Power Farm	1.97
	Open Field PVs	0.70
	Rooftop PVs	0.60
2038	Diesel Power Plant	0.80
	Open Field PVs	3.53
	Rooftop PVs	1.20
2052	Diesel Power Plant	0.00
	Open Field PVs	12.71
	Rooftop PVs	2.41

Table 5.5 Scenario 2: Diesel Power Plant & RES Proposed Installed Capacities

Figure 5.9 Scenario 2: Diesel Power Plant & RES Proposed Installed Capacities

5.3.2 Battery Energy Storage System

Based on the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES for the years 2022, 2030, 2038 and 2052, as outlined in subsection 5.3.1, the capacity and power for the required BESS for the same years, taking into account that will have a maximum storage duration of 4 hours[21], are illustrated in the Table 5.6.

Year	Capacity (MWh)	Power (MW)
2022	-	-
2030	4	1
2038	20	5
2052	80	20

Table 5.6 Scenario 2: BESS Capacity & Power

5.3.3 Demand Coverage

The Figure 5.10 illustrates the percentage of electricity production from the diesel power plant, and open field and rooftop photovoltaics for the years 2022, 2030, 2038, and 2052, based on the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES and BESS capacity and power, as outlined in subsection 5.3.1 and subsection 5.3.2. In 2022, the demand is entirely supplied by the diesel power plant. In 2030, RES comprise 30% of the electricity production, increasing to 92% in 2038, and achieving complete coverage of demand in 2052.

Figure 5.10 Scenario 2: Electricity Production Percentage

The Figure 5.11, Figure 5.12, Figure 5.13, and Figure 5.14 illustrate the TS of electricity production from the diesel power plant, and open field and rooftop pho-

to voltaics for the years 2022, 2030, 2038, and 2052, as well as the stored electrical energy in the BESS, based on the proposed installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES and BESS capacity and power, as outlined in subsection 5.3.1 and subsection 5.3.2.

Figure 5.11 Scenario 2: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2022

Figure 5.12 Scenario 2: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2030

Figure 5.13 Scenario 2: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2038

Figure 5.14 Scenario 2: Electricity Production & Demand Coverage TS for the Year 2052

5.3.4 Electricity Production & Distribution Schema

The Figure 5.15 illustrates the electricity production and distribution in Kastellorizo for scenario 2. Light green shading represents infrastructure initiate installation in 2030. Light pink shading represents the diesel section decommissioned in 2030, red in 2038, and darker red in 2052.

Figure 5.15 Scenario 2: Electricity Production & Distribution Schema

5.4 Comparison of Scenarios 1 & 2

5.4.1 Installed Capacities

As depicted in the Figure 5.16, the installed capacities of the diesel power plant and rooftop photovoltaics remain consistent between both scenarios. However, in scenario 2, where the onshore wind park is not existed, there is an almost double requirement for the installed capacity of open field photovoltaics to meet the demand in 2052.

Figure 5.16 Comparison: Diesel Power Plant & RES Proposed Installed Capacities

5.4.2 Battery Energy Storage System

As depicted in the Figure 5.17, in scenario 2, where the onshore wind park is not existed and there is an almost double requirement for the installed capacity of open field photovoltaics to meet the demand in 2052, the maximum capacity and power of the BESS are 1.5 times greater in the aforementioned year. That means that in scenario 2, an additional area is needed for the BESS in order to achieve complete decarbonization of Kastellorizo.

Figure 5.17 Comparison: BESS Capacity & Power

5.4.3 Demand Coverage

The demand coverage percentage between the two scenarios considered and analyzed in this study, both achieving the complete decarbonization of the island, is depicted in the Figure 5.18.

Figure 5.18 Comparison: Demand Coverage Percentage

Chapter 6

Further Development

6.1 Renewable Energy Assessment and Installation

The following maps, Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2, showcase data obtained from py-GRETA, highlighting the wind and solar energy potential on both Kastellorizo and Stroggili in locations that the RES infrastructure could be installed. This assessment is based on Full Load Hours (FLH), which represent the total number of hours per year during which RES generate electricity at their nominal power. Based on these maps, the installation of the proposed RES infrastructure, as outlined in subsection 5.2.1 and subsection 5.3.1, will proceed. Details regarding the maximum power potential for wind and solar energy, including open field and rooftop, on these islands along with the percentage of available land are provided in Table 5.2.

Figure 6.1 Kastellorizo & Stroggili Open Field & Rooftop Solar Potential Map[10]

When it comes to the onshore wind farm, installing the wind turbines on the Stroggili islet is suggested due to its substantial wind potential, as indicated on the map. Furthermore, placing these installations on uninhabited islets minimizes visual disturbances in the surrounding areas of Kastellorizo, as outlined in section 5.1.

Figure 6.2 Kastellorizo & Stroggili Onshore Wind Potential Map[10]

6.2 Electric Vehicle Transition

Based on the motorization rates for the South Aegean (EL42) by NUTS-2 regions map, which includes Kastellorizo, and is measured by the number of passenger cars per 1,000 inhabitants, the data indicated that in 2021, there were 373 passenger cars per 1,000 inhabitants[22]. Applying this rate to the population of Kastellorizo, which had 584 permanent residents in 2021[9], it can be estimated that the island had approximately 218 passenger cars in 2021

To facilitate the transition of Kastellorizo's transportation sector to rely on EVs, it's essential to consider several factors. As of 2021, the European Union's average EV-to-charger ratio stood at 14[23], suggesting that Kastellorizo would need around 16 EV chargers. Considering the 1.7% growth in passenger vehicles in Greece from 2020 to 2021[24], and the various modes of transportation on the island, including taxis, buses, and boats[25], there is a rising demand for additional EV charging infrastructure. Furthermore, there's potential for electric transportation to expand to boats, possibly leading to an all-electric boat fleet by 2052.

It's important to consider that these estimates may vary during the summer months due to increased tourist activity, car rental agencies, and tourist buses, leading to a temporary surge in the number of vehicles on the island. Therefore, projecting a full transition to EVs by 2052 signifies a significant increase in demand for electricity and EV chargers

6.3 Biofuel Power Plants

With limited prospects for diesel development, the energy landscape is shifting towards RES[5], particularly in power generation. Solar, hydro, and wind energy are prominent options, yet their volatility and intermittence pose grid stability challenges. Solar thermal power generation offers a solution with continuous and stable output despite construction and environmental constraints[26]. In parallel, biomass and biofuels emerge as pivotal players in transitioning to sustainable energy sources. Biomass, the world's fourth-largest energy source, boasts abundance, wide distribution, and emissions reduction benefits, making it an attractive choice amid rising fossil fuel costs. Currently, biomass fulfils around 10% of global energy demand, solidifying its role among renewables[27][28].

One promising avenue is the transformation of conventional diesel power plants into biofuel power plants. This shift not only reduces environmental consequences associated with diesel fuel but also aligns with the broader global trend toward large-scale development of RES, particularly for power generation. Moreover, by utilizing biofuels, the need for extensive BESS is significantly reduced, further enhancing the overall efficiency and sustainability of the energy infrastructure. Biomass-derived liquid fuels, such as bioethanol and biodiesel, have garnered significant attention due to their high energy density, convenient storage, and broad applicability[29].

For instance, bio oil, produced through processes like fast pyrolysis[30], offers a volumetric energy density up to 10 times higher than raw biomass and facilitates easy transportation. Countries like the United States, the United Kingdom, and Turkey have made significant strides in biomass power generation, reducing carbon emissions and boosting economic growth. As policies and financial support continue to encourage the development of biomass energy industries and related products, the prospect of transforming diesel power plants into biofuel-based facilities becomes increasingly viable. This transition aligns with the global imperative to enhance energy sustainability, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and ensure a reliable energy supply for the future.

In the context of the Kastellorizo case study, this conversion could be implemented for the third section of the diesel power plant, which is scheduled to operate until 2052, as indicated in Table 5.1. Converting the two diesel-based electricity generators, G1 and G2, each with an installed capacity of 0.4 MW, into biofuel-based generators could significantly reduce environmental impacts for the year 2038 in both scenarios 1 and 2. Additionally, in a new scenario where the operating licenses of electricity generators G1 and G2 are renewed in 2052, having these two

generators now operating on biofuel and contributing a maximum of 4% of electricity production, along with the existing renewable energy infrastructure in 2052, could result in a decreased requirement for BESS for the year 2052.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

In this internship report, a detailed examination has been conducted into the critical energy challenges faced by Kastellorizo, one of Greece's non-interconnected islands. The island's heavy reliance on diesel, along with the associated high CO₂ emissions and increased electricity production cost, underscore the urgent need for a transition towards RES and a decarbonized future. This situation not only poses environmental concerns but also places a financial burden on consumers through public service obligations. This research internship has focused on developing two distinct scenarios for Kastellorizo. Scenario 1 incorporates a combination of RES, including open field and rooftop photovoltaics, and an onshore wind farm. Scenario 2, on the other hand, contemplates the island's energy production exclusively from solar energy. In 2052, both scenarios envision Kastellorizo relying entirely on RES, reducing its environmental footprint, electricity production cost, and gradually decommissioning the existing diesel power plant until 2052. To facilitate this shift, detailed insights into the necessary installed capacities for the diesel power plant and RES, BESS specifications, and demand coverage projections for the key years 2030, 2038, and 2052 have been provided to enable the transition of Kastellorizo to a decarbonized energy model. BESS plays a pivotal role in maintaining a stable and reliable energy supply, ensuring energy availability during periods of low RES electricity generation. Additionally, potential locations for installing the proposed RES infrastructure have been identified based on the wind and solar energy potential on both Kastellorizo and the nearby Stroggili islet. Installing wind turbines on Stroggili, given its significant wind potential, can minimize visual disturbances in the surrounding areas of Kastellorizo. Furthermore, the potential transformation of the two diesel-based electricity generators into biofuel-based ones promises significant environmental benefits in 2038 and could reduce the need for BESS in 2052. In summary, this research internship outlines a possible path for Kastellorizo's energy transformation. By embracing RES, electric transportation, and potentially biofuel-based power generation, the island can significantly reduce its environmental footprint, lower electricity production costs, and ensure a prosperous future for its residents and visitors.

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